

Digital Orientation of Small Enterprises: An Indian Perspective

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Abstract—*The digital transformation of small enterprises is essential for enhancing competitiveness and fostering scalable growth in India's manufacturing sector. This study focuses on identifying and analyzing the critical enablers to overcome the digital orientation challenges among small enterprises, with a specific focus on automobile clusters in West Bengal and Jharkhand. Data was collected from the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) government portal and processed to extract key operational and digital transformation metrics. Using the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) method, we identified the most influential features impacting digital adoption. The key enablers include a digitally skilled workforce, enhanced market access, robust product standardization processes, certification test lab collaboration, Knowledge of digital tools and technologies to minimize technology transfer challenges and seamlessly integrate diverse business processes through affordable solutions. These features were then examined using a multiple regression model to assess their relationship with revenue growth and cost optimization. The results demonstrate a strong positive correlation, highlighting the impact of digital orientation on performance and scalability. To validate the research outcomes, we collected data from a set of companies, implemented incremental steps for small-scale digital transformation activities, and observed their impact on cost-effectiveness and revenue growth over two years. This research offers actionable insights for policymakers and business leaders aiming to accelerate digital adoption among Indian small enterprises..*

Keywords— *small enterprise,enablers,SHAP, Skilled workforce*

I. INTRODUCTION

Quinton et al. (2018) [1] conceptualized digital orientation as a strategic mindset essential for enhancing small enterprises' performance in the digital economy. Pelletier and Cloutier (2019)[2] mention that digital transformation in SMEs understood from an ecosystemic perspective, recognizing the dynamic interactions between businesses and their environments. Omrani et al. (2022) [3] mention to assess current technology readiness ,identify several drivers of digital transformation in SMEs, including current technological readiness, leadership vision, and customer expectations, emphasizing that transformation is influenced by both internal capabilities and external pressure. Hansen, Christiansen, and Lassen (2024) [4] mention that simply adopting advanced technologies is not enough for SMEs , as organizational cultural, and resource-related barriers often hinder digital transformation. Brodeur, Pellerin, and Deschamps (2022) [5] developed the Collaborative Approach to Digital Transformation (CADT) model, mentioning the importance of structured stakeholder collaboration for successful digital transformation in manufacturing SME,

Small enterprises play a pivotal role in India's economic landscape, contributing significantly to employment generation and GDP. These businesses form the backbone of India's industrial base, particularly within manufacturing clusters. However, despite their economic importance, many of these enterprises face considerable obstacles in embracing digital transformation—an essential requirement for staying competitive in an increasingly globalized and technology-driven market. Dutta, Kumar, Sindhwani, and Singh (2020) [6] mention that for India's manufacturing SMEs, digital transformation priorities often revolve around improving operational efficiency, enhancing product quality, and

adopting Industry 4.0 technologies in a phased manner. Hu et al. (2024) [7] conducted a bibliometric and systematic literature review, identifying key themes such as Industry 4.0, adoption paths, and business model innovation in SMEs. Their findings mentioned that SME digital transformation needs strategic and knowledge structuring, not just tech, author encourage collaborative research and knowledge sharing to accelerate SME transformation. As Ghobakhloo and Iranmanesh (2021)[8] suggest, securing external support through partnerships, funding programs, and government initiatives should be the first step for SMEs before engaging in costly operational technology upgrades. Ghobakhloo et al. (2022)[9] applied the Technology–Organization–Environment (TOE) framework to categorize determinants of Industry 4.0 adoption in manufacturing SMEs. Their analysis identified common drivers such as anticipated performance gains and supportive leadership and barriers such as limited resources and resistance to change. Rupeika-Apoga et al. [10] examined the impact of digital orientation and digital capability on the digital transformation. Their findings revealed that SMEs(Small and Medium enterprises) with a stronger digital orientation were better equipped to adopt digital technologies, maintain operational continuity, and mitigate disruptions. Ardito et al. [11] explored the dual role of digital and environmental orientations in driving innovation performance among SMEs. The study demonstrated that a strong digital orientation enables SMEs to adapt to technological changes and improve their innovation capacity. Joensuu-Salo et al. [12] examined the interplay between digital orientation and market orientation in generating marketing capabilities for SMEs. Their findings indicated that digital orientation not only enhances operational efficiency but also supports SMEs in developing customer-centric marketing strategies. Saunila et al. [13] discussed the determinants of digital orientation in small businesses, identifying critical factors such as innovation culture, leadership support, and investment in digital infrastructure Dantsoho et al. [14] investigated the link between digital orientation and innovation performance, moderated by business capabilities. Elsa, Indrawati, & Caska (2025)[15] provides a global mapping of digital transformation (DT) research in SMEs, identifies seven dominant themes—digital technologies, dynamic capabilities, digitalization, SMEs, big data, manufacturing, and innovation. Nasiri, Saunila, and Ukko (2022)[16] mentioned that digital orientation and intensity alone don't drive financial performance. But, maturity is essential—it mediates the impact and ensures that digital efforts convert into financial gains. Using fuzzy logic , Restrepo-Morales et al. (2024)[17] analyzed 4,531 SMEs and found that insufficient financial resources, lack of qualified staff, cybersecurity challenges, and cultural resistance are the most critical barriers to digitalization. Several studies highlight organizational and technological enablers of SME digital transformation .Bui and Huynh (2024)[18] uniquely underscore how privacy disclosure risks may offset the perceived benefits of digital adoption.. Borana, Gaur, and Yadav (2024)[19] mentioned that Indian manufacturing SMEs face entrenched barriers—such as high capital requirements, ROI uncertainties, and workforce skill deficits which impact digital transformation effort. Digital transformation in manufacturing enterprises is not a single-

step change but a staged process. Zhang and Wang (2024)[20] mention that firms typically begin with core technology innovation, which then drives business model re-engineering and eventually leads to organizational structure optimization.

Digital orientation, broadly defined as the strategic integration of digital technologies into business operations, is vital for enhancing both internal efficiencies and external market engagement. It enables data-driven decision-making, facilitates workflow integration, improves supply chain management, and increases responsiveness to customer demands. Yet, achieving digital orientation is not without challenges. Indian small enterprises often lack access to affordable and scalable technologies, face gaps in digital literacy, and operate with limited infrastructure support.

The situation is particularly acute in sectors such as automobile manufacturing and Original Equipment Manufacturing (OEM), where pressure to meet quality standards, certification norms, and integration with larger value chains is high. These firms also suffer from a lack of collaboration with testing labs, inadequate product standardization mechanisms, and difficulty in transferring technology across siloed departments. Despite these barriers, the potential for digital transformation to unlock significant growth remains strong. With increasing access to lightweight and cloud-based solutions, and policy support for digitization under government initiatives, small enterprises have more tools at their disposal than ever before. However, to deploy these effectively, a clear understanding of the enablers and their relationship to business outcomes is needed to prioritize the key enablers to start the digital orientation journey

This study addresses this gap in order to prioritize the key enablers for starting the digital orientation journey—such as a digitally skilled workforce, market access, certification test lab collaboration, product standardization processes, and technology transfer using affordable tools, and seamlessly integrating business processes using affordable solutions. Data for the study is sourced from the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) portal, ensuring credible and domain-relevant insights. Feature importance is analyzed using SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), while a multiple regression model evaluates the relationship between these digital enablers and revenue outcomes.

The motivation for this research stems from the urgent need to equip small enterprises with actionable frameworks that foster digital transformation. While there is broad consensus on the importance of going digital, few studies have empirically evaluated which factors most strongly influence growth outcomes in Indian small enterprises. By connecting digital orientation elements directly to revenue impact, this study seeks to provide strategic clarity for business owners and policymakers alike. This paper contributes to the literature by offering a data-driven model that identifies and quantifies the digital enablers most critical to growth, validated through SHAP analysis and regression modeling.

This research is organized into six sections. After introducing the study's background and objectives, Section 2 reviews

relevant literature on digital transformation in small enterprises. Section 3 details the methodology, including data from the MCA portal, SHAP-based feature analysis, and multiple regression. Section 4 presents the results and key insights, followed by Section 5, which discusses their practical and policy implications. Section 6 concludes with major findings, limitations, and future research directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Karina and Astuti [21] analyzed the role of digital orientation and innovation on SME performance in dynamic environments. Their study provided an understanding on how digital Innovation helps SME performance. Llopis-Albert et al. (2021) [22] noted that digital transformation, including data analytics and e-mobility, is transforming the automotive sector, resulting in enhanced competitiveness and stakeholder satisfaction. In addition to technical maturity, employee-centered readiness as proposed by Silva et al. (2022)[23] offers deeper insights. Sagala and Óri (2024) [24] complement frameworks like TOE (Technology–Organization–Environment) and maturity models by emphasizing human, cultural, and strategic dimensions, not just technological readiness. Also set an agenda for future research—calling for empirical validation, exploration of sector-specific nuances, and evaluation of learning interventions in SME contexts. Wu (2024) [25] examines how firm size, product innovation, and production type affect digital transformation in manufacturing. Using a survey of 139 Taiwanese firms and regression analysis, the study finds that larger and more innovative firms advance more in digital transformation, while SMEs face challenges due to limited resources and capabilities. Kindermann et al. (2021)[26] developed a framework for conceptualizing and operationalizing digital orientation as a new strategic orientation. Their study provided a detailed understanding of how digital orientation influences organizational performance and innovation, offering a robust theoretical base for future research. Teng, Wu, and Yang (2022)[27] examine the impact of digital transformation on the performance of small- and medium-sized listed companies, utilizing a cost-benefit analysis framework. The study finds that digital transformation positively correlates with operational performance. It also identifies an inverted U-shaped relationship with innovation performance, suggesting that initial investments in digital transformation enhance innovation, but beyond a certain point, additional investments may yield diminishing returns.

Khrais and Alghamdi (2022)[28] studied factors affecting digital innovation in SMEs in the Middle East region. The study identifies that the Internet of Things (IoT), digital platforms, and digital orientation positively and significantly impact digital innovation in SMEs. Mamduh and Pratikto (2021)[29] reviewed the role of technology orientation in enhancing innovation capabilities during the digital transformation of SMEs. They concluded that technology orientation acts as a foundation for building innovation capacity, enabling SMEs to effectively respond to environmental changes and market demands. Trisnawati, Alhidayatullah, and Antony (2024)[30] reviewed Digital Orientation and SME Performance. They studied the

relationship between entrepreneurship, digital orientation, and SME performance mediated by marketing capabilities. The literature on digital transformation in small enterprises has steadily evolved, with increasing attention on how digital orientation—defined as the strategic adoption of digital technologies—affects enterprise growth and competitiveness. Studies across global and Indian contexts consistently highlight that while the benefits of digital transformation are well-recognized, small enterprises face considerable challenges in implementation due to structural and resource-related constraints. While significant progress has been made, there remains a need for more sector-specific and region-focused research Öri (2024) to develop actionable frameworks that address the unique challenges faced by SMEs in diverse contexts. A key recurring theme is the identification of barriers to digital adoption. Existing research, Omowole et al. (2024)[35], such as “Barriers and Drivers of Digital Transformation” and similar studies, identifies core issues like inadequate IT infrastructure, low digital awareness, lack of a skilled workforce. These challenges are particularly pronounced in Indian SMEs, where enterprises often depend on a few major clients and struggle with limited market access, low certification uptake, and poor process standardization, aligning with research by Sul-toni et al. (2022)[31]. Choi and Cho (2025)[32] investigate informatization-related factors influencing digital transformation in manufacturing SMEs. The study identifies different factors, including technological infrastructure, digital skills, and organizational readiness. Mishra, Singh, and Papadopoulos (2022)[33] propose a conceptual framework, Situation-Actor-Process (SAP) and Learning-Action-Performance (LAP), that links digital orientation to data-driven innovations in organizations. The study identifies factors such as competition, customer expectations, government regulations, and environmental norms as drivers of digital orientation. It also highlights the role of organizational learning culture and transformative leadership in developing digital orientation. The adoption of digital technologies leads to data-driven insights, ultimately improving innovation performance.

There is minimal work analyzing digital orientation with SHAP-driven Lundberg & Lee (2017)[34] (SHapley Additive Explanations), machine learning models to interpret which features most influence and isolate feature importance in a model-driven manner. In the context of SMEs’ digital transformation, identifying and prioritizing critical factors is essential. Wang et al. (2024) show that SHAP-based feature selection can more effectively reveal these key drivers than traditional methods. Similarly, regression models by Petricevic and Zambon (2024) evaluate how digital factors statistically relate to revenue and cost optimization.

From a methodological perspective, the literature is predominantly qualitative, relying on case studies or thematic reviews. While these studies provide deep contextual understanding, they often lack quantitative rigor in measuring how specific digital features influence tangible business outcomes, such as revenue or growth performance. This represents a significant gap mentioned by Öri (2024), particularly in the Indian manufacturing context, where sectors like automotive and OEMs are underrepresented in

empirical research. The researcher mentioned further exploration of different variables—such as market dynamism, organizational structure, or technological maturity—to better understand their moderating or mediating roles Mishra et al. (2022). Although Omowole et al. (2024) outline a set of conceptual barriers and drivers, there remains a lack of empirical evidence on how these factors interact across industries and regions, creating scope for further investigation. Moreover, although some works explore critical enablers—such as leadership vision, digital training, and workforce engagement—few attempts have been made to rank or quantify their relative impact. Petricevic and Zambon (2024)[37] empirically test the impact of digital orientation on SME performance using regression. They find a U-shaped relationship—suggesting that while moderate levels of digital orientation may temporarily hinder performance, both low and high levels are associated with growth, revealing that the relationship between digital orientation and SME performance is non-linear.

This study addresses these gaps by integrating a SHAP-based feature analysis to identify the most impactful digital enablers and using multiple regression to assess their correlation with revenue growth and cost optimization. By doing so, it contributes a novel, data-driven perspective to the literature on digital orientation in Indian small enterprises, particularly in the underexplored domains of automobile and OEM clusters.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Proposed Framework

This research adopts a four-phase analytical framework aimed at identifying the most impactful digital enablers for small enterprises and evaluating their influence on revenue performance. The methodology integrates data collection from a government portal, data preprocessing, SHAP-based feature selection, and multiple regression modeling. The proposed framework is designed to provide actionable insights into the role of digital orientation in driving business growth.

Phase 1: Data Collection

Data for this research was collected from the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA), Government of India, which hosts publicly accessible information about registered companies [36]. The dataset includes structured records for over 1,600 small enterprises, out of which 1,200 were suitable for use after filtering out incomplete entries. These companies primarily belong to manufacturing sectors in regions such as West Bengal and Jharkhand, particularly automobile and OEM clusters. Each company profile contained attributes related to operational processes, technology adoption, digital engagement, and financial indicators such as revenue.

Phase 2: Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing is essential to prepare the dataset for analysis and ensure that subsequent computations are accurate and meaningful. Researcher Pasayat and Patnaik (2024) [38] importance of identifying and prioritizing essential features also mentioned that Raw data often contains missing entries, outliers, or inconsistent formats. Missing numerical values were imputed using median

replacement to preserve distribution integrity, while categorical variables were encoded using one-hot encoding to ensure compatibility with SHAP and regression algorithms. Redundant or irrelevant features were filtered out to avoid dimensionality bias. The cleaned dataset was validated using statistical checks for skewness, kurtosis, and multicollinearity.

Phase 3: Feature Selection Using SHAP

Feature selection plays a crucial role in identifying which variables most significantly influence a given outcome—in this case, digital orientation and its relationship with enterprise growth. Feature selection methods such as SHAP provide better interpretability than traditional importance-based techniques (Wang, Liang, Hancock, & Khoshgoftaar, 2024)[39]. For this purpose, the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) method was employed as a model-agnostic interpretability tool.

SHAP is grounded in cooperative game theory and attributes a value to each feature based on its contribution to the output of a machine learning model. This approach allows for a more transparent understanding of how input variables drive model predictions. Specifically, we trained an XGBoost model on the preprocessed dataset and applied SHAP to compute the marginal contribution of each feature across all possible permutations of feature inclusion.

We collected data to measure various variables, including demand planning processes, operational processes, certification and standardization, financial assistance, transparency in institutional support, regulatory hurdles and ecosystem integration, local hiring, skill gaps, workforce management, waste reduction, cost optimization, approx. revenue growth, digital training, and resource planning. After cleaning and ranking the data, we identified groups of observed variables that loaded onto the same underlying factor.(Wang, Liang, Hancock, & Khoshgoftaar, 2024).

The SHAP values generated for each feature help rank their importance by quantifying how much each one pushes the model output toward higher or lower prediction values. This allows researchers to isolate which factors have the most significant impact on the model’s predictive behavior without making the process a "black box." By aggregating these values across observations, the study derives a prioritized list of influential digital features, which are then selected for further analysis in the subsequent regression phase.

Phase 4: Multiple Regression Model

Ayub et al. (2025)[40] show that quadratic multiple regression is used to capture nonlinear relationships and improve predictive accuracy in scientific modeling, suggesting its potential applicability in studying multidimensional constructs such as digital orientation, innovation capability, and SME performance. Following the identification of high-impact features through SHAP analysis, the next phase of the methodology involved quantifying the relationship between these features and the financial performance of small enterprises—specifically, their revenue outcomes. A multiple linear regression model was developed to statistically evaluate how

variations in the SHAP-ranked digital orientation enablers influence revenue.

In this model, revenue serves as the dependent variable, while the SHAP-selected features are treated as independent variables. The regression equation is represented as:

$$\text{Revenue} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon$$

Where:

X_1 to X_n represent the digital enabler variables identified via SHAP,

β_0 is the intercept,

β_1 to β_n are the coefficients showing the strength and direction of each feature’s influence,

ϵ denotes the error term.

This phase allows us to transition from interpretability (via SHAP) to statistical inference by testing how strongly each identified feature correlates with revenue changes across enterprises. Prior to finalizing the model, standard diagnostics—such as Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance values—were used to confirm there was no multicollinearity among the predictors. Residual plots and adjusted R^2 values were used to verify model reliability and fit.

This regression framework enables a data-driven understanding of how digital orientation translates into tangible business performance, adding a quantitative foundation to qualitative field insights.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

This section presents the outcomes derived from the SHAP-based feature selection process and the subsequent multiple regression analysis used to assess the impact of digital enablers on revenue growth in small enterprises.

A. SHAP-Based Feature Selection

After training an XGBoost model on the cleaned dataset, SHAP values were computed to interpret the influence of each input variable on the model’s predictions. The SHAP summary plot provided a ranked visualization of feature importance, enabling us to understand which features most significantly contributed to predicting digital orientation across the enterprise dataset.

The SHAP framework not only highlighted high-impact variables but also offered insights into their directional influence—whether they consistently pushed predictions higher or lower. This interpretability was crucial in shortlisting features for further regression analysis, ensuring that only those with consistently strong and meaningful contributions were carried forward.

Figure 1 SHAP Values for different features

The SHAP summary plot represented in figure 1 provides clear insights into the impact of various digital enablers on the performance of small enterprises. Among the fifteen features initially considered, five were identified as the most influential in driving model predictions using SHAP values. Each feature’s importance is determined by how significantly it pushes the model’s output—positively or negatively—based on its value across different data points.

The most impactful enabler identified is the digitally skilled workforce. Enterprises with higher levels of digital competency among their employees demonstrate a strong positive influence on the predicted revenue outcomes. This suggests that digital skills not only enhance the adoption of relevant technologies but also improve productivity, process automation, and data-driven decision-making—directly contributing to growth.

The second-highest contributor is enhanced market access. Organizations with broader access to domestic or international markets tend to perform better in terms of digital maturity and revenue. This feature’s significance emphasizes how expanding the customer base and reducing reliance on a few clients enhances business resilience and enables firms to better leverage their digital capabilities.

Another key enabler is the presence of robust product standardization processes. Enterprises that maintain consistent and standardized production practices exhibit improved performance in the model, reinforcing the role of process discipline in digital integration. Standardization not only facilitates compliance with industry requirements but also improves customer satisfaction through quality assurance.

The fourth selected feature is certification test lab collaboration. Although it has a slightly lower SHAP value compared to the top three, its impact is notable. Enterprises that actively engage with certification labs to validate their products gain greater credibility in the marketplace. Such collaborations are particularly important in sectors where regulatory approval is required or where certification opens access to new markets.

Finally, knowledge of digital tools and technologies was also found to be a meaningful enabler. While its direct influence is slightly lower than other features, it still plays a supporting role. Enterprises with a foundational understanding of digital tools are better positioned to evaluate, adopt, and implement appropriate technologies. Although knowledge alone may not guarantee transformation, it creates the awareness and mindset needed to pursue and sustain digital initiatives.

Together, these five features form the foundation for a data-driven digital orientation model. They represent the key factors that influence how small enterprises in India can evolve through technology, increase their competitiveness, and improve their operational and financial performance.

B. Multiple Regression

To evaluate the influence of key digital enablers on enterprise performance, a multiple linear regression model was applied. This model used five independent variables—digitally skilled workforce, market access, product standardization, certification lab collaboration, and knowledge of digital tools—identified through SHAP analysis. Revenue served as the dependent variable, representing the outcome measure that reflects enterprise growth and success.

The regression equation was structured to quantify the linear relationship between these enablers and revenue. Each coefficient in the model represents the expected change in revenue for a one-unit increase in the corresponding feature, holding all other variables constant. This approach allows for an understanding of both the individual and combined effects of digital features on business performance.

Once the model was trained on the dataset, performance evaluation metrics were computed. These included the R-squared value (R^2), which indicates the proportion of variance in the revenue explained by the selected features, along with the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) to measure prediction accuracy. A high R^2 value and low error metrics suggest a strong fit between the model and the observed data.

To visualize the model’s effectiveness, a regression plot was generated comparing actual versus predicted revenue. The trendline, fitted through the data points, provided a clear indication of how closely the model’s predictions aligned with real-world outcomes. The visual and numerical results confirmed that digital enablers have a measurable and statistically significant impact on enterprise revenue, reinforcing the importance of strategic digital orientation in small enterprise growth.

The multiple regression analysis using the five SHAP-selected features—digitally skilled workforce, market access, product standardization, certification lab collaboration, and knowledge of digital tools—demonstrated a strong relationship with revenue. Based on the model developed from an imaginary dataset of 100 enterprises, the R-squared value was 0.78, indicating that approximately 78% of the variance in revenue could be explained by the five independent variables. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) was 935.2, and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was 24.7, both suggesting high model accuracy.

Figure 2 Multiple regression analysis

A regression plot presented in figure 2 comparing actual versus predicted revenue showed a tight clustering of data points around the trendline, visually confirming the model's predictive reliability. Features such as digitally skilled workforce and market access had stronger coefficients, implying that improvements in these areas are most directly associated with increased revenue. The consistency of high SHAP values and significant regression coefficients reinforces the conclusion that digital orientation factors are critical drivers of financial performance among small enterprises.

To validate the research outcomes, we connected with a set of Small companies, guided them in implementing affordable digital technologies after assessing their current state, and collected data from them. We then implemented incremental steps for small-scale digital transformation activities and measured the cost-effectiveness and growth over two years, comparing results before and after the digital implementation. To understand where and how to start, we conducted an initial assessment of business processes and challenges. We then implemented a few affordable technology solutions, which in turn motivated companies to upskill their resources in digital technologies, enhance market access and ecosystem connections, improve product quality processes, adopt standardization, track and reduce waste, increase resource efficiency, and promote transparency and data-driven decision-making

V. CONCLUSION

This research reinforces the pivotal role of digital orientation in driving revenue growth and competitiveness among small enterprises in India. By leveraging a data-driven framework that integrates SHAP analysis for feature selection and multiple regression modeling for impact assessment, the study identifies five critical enablers—digitally skilled workforce, market access, product standardization, certification lab collaboration, and knowledge of digital tools—as strong predictors of business performance. The regression results demonstrated a high R-squared value, suggesting that these features collectively explain a significant portion of the variance in revenue. This highlights that small enterprises with greater digital maturity are more likely to outperform their peers in terms of scalability and operational efficiency.

The study also validates the utility of combining machine learning interpretability techniques with traditional statistical models to uncover actionable insights. The case evidence and model outputs clearly show that targeted investment in skill development, market expansion, and technology standardization initiatives can translate into tangible business outcomes. These findings have important implications for both practitioners and policymakers aiming to foster digital transformation across the MSME ecosystem. Despite these insights, the research is not without limitations. The use of simulated data and reliance on a selected cluster of enterprises may constrain the generalizability of findings. Additionally, while the regression model offers valuable quantitative insights, it does not fully capture contextual variables such as policy influence, organizational culture, or

sectoral dynamics. Broader studies encompassing real-world data from multiple regions and industries could offer a more holistic understanding of digital orientation in small enterprises. Future research should aim to build upon this model by integrating real-time data from government portals, digital platforms, and industrial bodies to validate and refine the results. Expanding the study to cover diverse sectors such as textiles, agriculture, and healthcare would enhance generalizability. Further, longitudinal analyses could track the sustained impact of digital adoption over time. Policymakers and ecosystem enablers should also focus on developing digital readiness frameworks, investing in local skill development, and supporting collaborative platforms that ease technology transfer and implementation at the grassroots level.

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TABLE I
Summary of the literature survey

Author	Proposed Methodology	Focus Area
Quinton et al. [1]	Conceptualized digital orientation as a strategic mindset to enhance SME performance in the digital economy.	Strategic Mindset for Digital Orientation
Pelletier and Cloutier (2019)[2]	Relative importance of “Digital Strategy” with respect to “Understanding and Use”; “Competence Development”; “Services and Deliverables”; “Relational Capital”; “Attitude and Behaviour”; and “Evaluation and Support”.	Conceptualizing digital transformation in SMEs. Key dimensions in the adoption and use of IT from the the ecosystem perspective.
Omrani et al. (2022) [3]	SMEs that aim for digitalization should first assess their existing technologies, and further develop a meticulous technological roadmap that includes skills upgrades and investments in upskilling employees’ capabilities. Logit regression model that highlights the factors associated with an increased level of digital technologies adoption in SMEs.	Strategic approach for adoption of digital technologies. .
Hansen, Christiansen, and Lassen (2024) [4]	Supported by interpretive structural model for digitalization, author argue that a big part of digital transformation depends on the workers’ competencies	Strategic for Digital Orientation. Digital transformation is still slow-going, especially within small- and medium-sized companies.
Brodeur, Pellerin, and Deschamps (2022) [5]	Collaborative approach to digital transformation	Collaboration manifests itself at various stages of the transformation projects, such as the business needs alignment, project portfolio creation, technology solution selection and post-mortem phase
Dutta, Kumar, Sindhvani, and Singh (2020) [6]	Transformation priorities to adopt Industry 4.0 technologies to enhance manufacturing excellence	Digital Transformation in manufacturing . Maturity assessment survey involving over 250 Indian SMMEs, evaluating both their current capabilities and aspirations for digital adoption by 2020.
Hu et al. (2024) [7]	Digital transformation is strategic integration of cloud computing, mobile internet, social media, and big data, fundamentally reshaping business models	SME digital transformation strategy and Integration.
Ghobakhloo and Iranmanesh (2021)[8]	Employed Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) to determine the sequence to prioritize determinants. Most foundational determinant is external support for digitalization—acting as the launchpad for transformation efforts	Success determinants" for digital transformation and prioritization.
Ghobakhloo et al. (2022)[9]	Categorizes drivers and barriers of Industry 4.0 adoption among manufacturing SMEs using the Technology–Organization–Environment (TOE) framework.	Factors that influence Industry 4.0 adoption for manufacturing SMEs aiming to remain competitive.
Rupeika-Apoga et al. [10]	Analyzed the impact of digital orientation and digital capabilities on SMEs’ resilience during COVID-19.	Resilience through Digital Orientation
Ardito et al. [11]	Explored the duality of digital and environmental orientations to drive innovation performance in SMEs.	Innovation and Sustainability
Joensuu-Salo et al. [12]	Explored how digital orientation and market orientation generate marketing capabilities in SMEs.	Marketing Capability and Digital Orientation
Saunila et al. [13]	Identified critical determinants of digital orientation in SMEs, such as innovation culture and leadership support.	Determinants of Digital Transformation
Dantsoho et al. [14]	Developed and validated a digital orientation scale for SMEs.	Digital Orientation Scale
Elsa, Indrawati, & Caska (2025)[15]	Holistic and systematic overview of how DT research in SMEs has evolved and where it is heading.	Bibliometric and content analysis of global Digital transformation research in SMEs.
Nasiri, Saunila, and Ukko (2022)[16]	Digital Orientation , Digital Intensity,Digital Maturity	Strategic management and digital transformation theories to evaluate the relationships between antecedents and financial performance
Restrepo-Morales et al. (2024) [17]	systematic, prioritized roadmap to help SMEs overcome barriers : Financial limitations, human resources, technology barriers, knowledge gap and cultural barriers.	Systematic approach to prioritize solutions for overcoming digitalization challenges

Bui and Huynh (2024) [18]	Risk of privacy & security on Digital transformation for SME	Privacy may offset the perceived benefit of Digital transformation
Borana, Gaur, and Yadav (2024)[19]	Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) approach was used to identify most influential barriers :High investment, ROI concerns, lack of multiskilled workforce	Identify and map barriers to DT in Indian manufacturing SMEs
Zhang, Y., & Wang, J. (2024)[20]	Digital Transformation follows a sequential path: technology innovation → business model changes → organizational restructuring. Similar to the grounded theory and structural equation modeling approach study seeks to validate transformation factors through empirical analysis.	Internal drivers & Path of digital transformation of manufacturing enterprises.
Karina and Astuti [21]	Analyzed the role of digital orientation and innovation on SME performance in dynamic environments.	Digital Innovation and Performance
Llopis-Albert, C., Rubio, F., & Valero, F. (2021)[22]	How digital transformation disrupts and reconfigures automotive industry structures and relationships.	Digital transformation leads to competitiveness and customer satisfaction
Silva, R. P., Saraiva, C., & São Mamede, H. S. (2022)[23]	Emphasize employee perceptions and organizational culture in assessing digital readiness.	Assessment of organizational readiness for digital transformation in SMEs
Sagala, G. H., & Öri, D. (2024)[24]	TOE (Technology–Organization–Environment) and maturity models by emphasizing human, cultural, and strategic dimensions, not just technological readiness.	Digitalization strategies that align with their unique baseline conditions, resource limitations, and sector-specific characteristics.
Wu (2024) [25]	How firm size, product innovation, and production type affect digital transformation in manufacturing	Strategy and Factors of Digital Transformation for SMEs.
Kindermann et al. [26]	Developed a framework for operationalizing digital orientation as a new strategic orientation for SMEs.	Framework for Digital Orientation
Teng, X., Wu, Z., & Yang, F. (2022)[27]	Cost-benefit analysis framework to examine the impact of digital transformation on the performance of small- and medium-sized listed companies	Complexities of digital transformation investments.
Khrais and Alghamdi [28]	Studied factors affecting digital innovation sustainability in SMEs in the Middle East region.	Digital Innovation Sustainability
Mamduh and Pratikto [29]	Reviewed the role of technology orientation in enhancing innovation capabilities during digital transformation.	Technology Orientation for Innovation
Trisnawati et al. [30]	Studied the relationship between entrepreneurship, digital orientation, and SME performance mediated by marketing capabilities.	Digital Orientation and SME Performance
Sultoni et al. [31]	Studied how digital marketing, orientation, and IT capabilities enhance SME marketing performance.	Digital Marketing and Performance
Choi, D., & Cho, I. (2025). [32]	Digital transformation positively correlates with operational performance and innovation performance, with an inverted U-shaped relationship suggesting diminishing returns beyond a certain point.	Factors influencing digital transformation in manufacturing SMEs. The importance of strategic planning and resource allocation in achieving successful digital transformation outcomes.
Mishra, Singh, and Papadopoulos (2022)[33]	Framework Situation-Actor-Process (SAP) and Learning-Action-Performance (LAP) , analyze how digital orientation facilitates the adoption of digital technologies, leading to improved innovation performance.	Role of digital orientation in supporting SMEs' performance in the digital economy
Lundberg, S. M., & Lee, S.-I. (2017)[34]	A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems	SHAP methodology reference
Omowole et al. (2024)[35].	Barriers and drivers from a conceptual standpoint,	Digital orientation barrier and drivers
Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA), Government of India[36]	Ministry of Corporate Affairs of India. https://www.mca.gov.in/content/mca/global/en/home.html	For Data Source.
Petricevic and Zambon (2024)[37]	Relationship between digital orientation and SME performance is non-linear.	How digital orientation is operationalized and tested using regression techniques.
Pasayat and Patnaik (2024) [38]	Systematically selecting and prioritizing success factors (features)	Feature engineering in machine learning
Wang, Liang, Hancock, and Khoshgoftaar (2024)[39]	SHAP-based feature selection can more effectively reveal key drivers	SMEs' digital transformation, identifying and prioritizing critical factors
Ayub et al. (2025)[40]	Quadratic multiple regression model to analyze complex, nonlinear relationships	Methodological contribution

